
THE PROCESS OF ESTABLISHMENT OF THE ASHTARKHANID STATE

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Abstract.

In this article , detailed information is given about the issues related to the rise of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty and the transition of the country to the stage of political development . In addition, in this article, the list of the rulers of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty is presented chronologically .

Key words.

Ashtarkhanids, Asrtrakhan, Abdullah Khan II, Bukhara Khanate, Samarkand, Baqi Muhammad Khan, Jonibek Sultan, Shaibanis.

Enter. Ashtarkhani Jani dynasty ruled the Khanate of Bukhara in 1601-1756. After the death of Abdullah Khan in 1598 , the struggle for the crown began among the Shaybanites, which eventually led to the complete collapse of this dynasty. By this time, none of the Shaybanites remained on the throne of Bukhara Khanate.

Results. After the conquest of Astrakhan by the Russians in 1556 (Khojitarkhan khanate), Jonibek, the son of Yormuhammad Khan, who fled to Bukhara during the conquest of this khanate, ruled Sultan They wanted to raise him as a khan (he will marry Abdullah Khan's sister Zuhrabegim) Jonibek Sultan has three sons from Zuhrabegim: Din Muhammad, Baqi Muhammad, Vali Muhammad. Jonibek Sultan and his sons achieved a high position in the Bukhara Khanate and performed the duties of governors in the provinces. Jonibek Sultan was offered the throne of Bukhara Khanate. Jonibek Sultan refused this offer. Amirs made his eldest son Dinmuhammad Khan. Dinmuhammad was in Obiward at this time. He died on the way to Bukhara. After that, in 1601, his brother Baqimuhammad became Khan. Janibek's third son, Valimuhammad, was declared the heir to the throne (waliahd) and was appointed viceroy of Balkh. From that time, in 1599, a new dynasty of the Ashtarkhanids, the "Jonis" (the name of the Janiys was taken from the name of the head of the clan Jonibek), was established in Movarounnahr, and this dynasty ruled the country for 175 years. Officially, the supreme power in this country was in the

hands of J onibek Sultan, coins were minted in his name, and his name was added to the sermon [1:155] .

During the reign of Baqi Muhammad, efforts were made to put an end to internal political disputes in the khanate, to strengthen the cohesion of the country's borders , and to protect the northern borders of the khanate from nomadic tribes. Baqi Muhammad expelled the Iranians from the Balkh region, subordinated a number of regions to the Khanate of Bukhara , and appointed his brother Wali Muhammad as governor. For Tashkent, in 1604, the Kazakh Khan Kelimhammad expelled his troops from the territory of the country and subjugated a number of areas to the Khanate of Bukhara. Many wars were fought with Kazakh sultans. After the death of Baqi Muhammad in 1605 , his brother Wali Muhammad ascended the throne.

During the reign of Wali Muhammad, the internal struggle flared up again. The chiefs of the tribe did not submit to the Khan's authority and strengthened the opposition. At the beginning of the 17th century, the territory of the Bukhara Khanate was much smaller than during the time of Abdullah Khan II . . . Ashtarkhanids will completely lose Khorezm and a large part of Khurasan . Wali Muhammad, who learned about the rebellion of the emirs against the khan, took his children and fled to Iran. During his relatively long reign (1611-1742), he managed to put an end to the feudal wars prevailing in the khanate and strengthen the central authority, but he was unable to recapture Khurasan and Khorezm. For the northern borders of Tashkent and the khanate, nomadic tribes successfully fought against the Kazakhs, Kalmyks, and Mongols and expanded the territory of the khanate to the northeast. During the period of Imam Quli Khan, the position of the Khan's authority increased, and the internal situation improved somewhat.

But during the reign of Nadir Muhammad Khan, Abdulaziz Khan and Subkhan Quli Khan, who sat on the throne after Imam Quli Khan, the political situation in the country went out of control again. These khans were forced to wage continuous wars against local feudal lords and external enemies.

these struggles, the main people of the government were the religious leaders. For this reason, during this period, land areas began to be transferred to religious courts and large scholars. Religious fanaticism increased. This, in turn, affected worldly development, hindered the development of the state and society. Incessant wars, excessively heavy taxes, and frequent natural disasters on top of local governors' tyranny have ruined the country's economic situation and weakened the people's condition even more. By the beginning of the 18th century, the crisis

situation in the Ashtarkhanid state intensified. During this period, they were completely subordinated to the chiefs of the Uzbek clans and the big court officials, they elevated the khans to the throne, deprived them of the throne, expelled them from the country or killed them . [2:147]

Ubaydullah Khan (1702-1711) is the last Ashtar Khan ruler who tried to strengthen the central power and end the political tyranny in the country. Ubaidullah Khan's monetary reform, which tried to weaken the economic power of the headless Uzbek emirs, fill the state treasury and improve the country's financial situation, further complicated the political and economic situation. Minted low-value copper coins were not taken by merchants in the markets, shops were closed, and a big riot broke out in the city of Bukhara. Although it was suppressed with great difficulty, the political and economic situation in the country did not improve. As a result, Ubaydullah Khan was killed, and the last Khan of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty, Abulfayz Khan, took the throne. During his reign (1712-1747), the rebellion of tribal chiefs and regional governors against the central government intensified. Conspiracy broke out among officials.

The rulers of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty

1. Boqi Muhammad 1601-1606 years
2. Wali Muhammad 1611-1611 years
3. Imamkuli Khan 1611-1642 years
4. Nadir Muhammad Khan 1642-1645 years
5. Abdullazizkhan 1645-1681 years
6. Subkh Ongulikhan 1681-1701 years
7. Ubaidullah Khan 1702-1711
8. Abulfayzkhan 1711-1747 years
9. Abdulmomin 1747-1751 years
10. Ubaidullah II 1751-1753 years
11. Shergozi 1754-1756 years.

Discussion. During the period of Abulfaiz Khan, the central authority lost its importance again. The country began to be divided into regions that consider themselves independent. The management of the country began to pass into the hands of Muhammad Hakimbi, who was supported by the Mangit clans and had a reputation among the great nobles. Abulfayzkhan was a khan only, the main authority was managed by influential emirs Javshan Kalmyk, then Qushbegi Abdullabi, and Muhammad Hakimbi fathers. The political disunity in the state increased, Balkh was separated from Bukhara, later the descendants of

Normammed from the Ashtar Khans, and various Uzbek princes ruled here. The rule of the Yorbek dynasty was established in Badakhshan. Khorezm became completely independent from Bukhara. In this way, the Ashtarkhanid dynasty ended completely. [3:220]

Summary. During the period of 1601-1756, the political and social disunity that prevailed during the Ashtarkhanid period, the mutual struggles for the throne between khans, sultans, and princes, wars of robbery caused our ancestors of that time to lag behind the world development. It's done.

In short, during the reign of the Ahtarkhanid dynasty, which came to power in the Bukhara Khanate, the process of economic and cultural development sometimes progressed, or on the contrary, there were cases of decline .

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